

How Gender and the Work Environment Influence the Job Satisfaction of Public Secondary School Teachers in the Central Region of Botswana

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Abstract

This study's main focus was to investigate how gender and the work environment influence the job satisfaction of public secondary school teachers in the Central region of Botswana. Maslow's theory of needs was used for the study. This study used quantitative analysis and targeted a population of 680 teachers from ten public secondary schools in the Central Region of Botswana. The sample of the study consisted of thirty-two percent of the targeted population which involved 213 teacher respondents. The participants were randomly selected from both junior and senior secondary schools in the region. A questionnaire was used during the data collection process and the validity and reliability of the instrument were established before the questionnaire was administered to the sampled participants. The efficiency of the questionnaire was pre-tested by 20 teacher respondents who were not part of the study sample. The data were presented using descriptive statistics, One Way Analysis Of Variance (ANOVA) and independent sample t-tests tables. The descriptive statistics used were calculated using the Statistical Packages of Social Scientists (SPSS). The findings of the study showed a strong link between gender, the work environment and teacher's job satisfaction. In the study, public secondary school male teachers had greater job satisfaction than their female counterparts. The study further revealed that males were satisfied with promotion than female teachers. The study made some recommendations that the school management should practice and ensure gender equality amongst teachers towards promotions for high posts.

Keywords: Gender; Job satisfaction; Work environment; Promotion.

Introduction

The success of any educational institution depends on teachers. As a result, studies on teachers' job satisfaction are crucial for the critical role that job satisfaction plays in various work aspects. It is evident that levels of job satisfaction felt by secondary school teachers in similar work environments can differ from one individual to the other. Some researchers therefore have discovered that, teachers' job satisfaction significantly link with job-related and workplace variables such as; gender, promotion and the work environment (Mabekoje, 2009). As such, for a nation to rise to a standard admirable enough for her to compete satisfactorily in the league of nations, such a nation must make sure that high quality education is provided and maintained and this can only be attained if a quality workforce is provided (Olufunke, Joseph & Adetayo, 2012). If the workforce in secondary schools is of high quality, there would be quality education which is a highly essential instrument in the transformation of the citizen's values, beliefs and even the behaviour. This would also safeguard the society's culture and assists in the attainment of skills which produce well-rounded members of the society which are helpful in the whole nation.

Specters (1997) indicates that job satisfaction has a strong connection with different variables such as; achievement, advancement, job enhancement, teamwork, promotion, cooperation, job stress, mentoring and training needs, management and recognition of success. He states that the level of job satisfaction is usually measured through employees feelings, among others about ; pay, the work itself, benefits, career advancement, promotion of teamwork and communication, personnel policies, concern for employees, training and development. In this manner, job satisfaction is fundamental to all employees as it; determines the retention of employees, motivation and efficiency as well as the happiness of the employees themselves and their customers. It is therefore believed that, a person's attitude influences their behaviour. Hence, a happy worker has more positive returns. However, very few organizations have considered job satisfaction as a top priority and this is detrimental to the productivity of such employees and the entire organisation (Gathungu & Wachira, 2013).

When investigating on the relationship between teachers' performance and the school environment, Adesina (2011) found out that the secondary school teachers' job satisfaction was greater when a conducive school environment was provided than in an unconducive atmosphere. Moreover, Nwachukwu and Anina (2014) established that the school environment in most Nigerian public secondary schools was poor and that did not encourage any learning amongst learners. Ananga (2012) further indicated that teaching and learning in public secondary schools were mostly affected by poor school environments and this created several challenges to teachers' productivity and learners' academic performance. These challenges according to Nwachukwu (2013) were as a result of poor climate change which led to poor education, inadequate resources for teaching and learning as well as deplorable working conditions.

Theoretical Background

This study was guided by Maslow's hierarchy of needs which is the widely recognized and mostly referenced theory of motivation. Maslow (1943) considered motivation as a continually changing desire to fulfil changing needs. He believed that human needs occurred in a hierarchy of importance, which he called 'prepotency'.

According to Maslow (1970), the needs of an individual exist in a logical order and the basic lower-level needs must be satisfied before the higher levels needs. Therefore, once the fundamental needs are fulfilled, they no longer serve as motivators for the individual. As such, the more a job allows for growth and acquisition of higher-level needs, the more the individual is likely to report satisfaction with his or her job. Besides, the success of motivating people depends on recognizing the needs that are unsatisfied and helping the individual to meet those needs.

Maslow (1943) as cited in Erkilic (2008) indicates that individuals are firstly motivated by Psychological needs. He regards these needs as the basic needs which people cannot survive without, including; foodstuff, clothes and accommodation. When people do not have the basic needs according to Maslow, what they at first wish for is to make sure that such needs are fulfilled. As a result, their behaviour is influenced by the need to acquire the basic needs than anything else. However, when people's basic needs are fulfilled, they tend to move to the security needs which Maslow views as the higher order of needs. These needs revolve around the safety in the employee's health and family.

Maslow further mentioned the social needs. Maslow (1943) points out that, when employees are safe at work, they work well with others. They therefore build up good friendships with their core-workers. As employees keep moving upwards, they have self-esteem needs: This level of needs as suggested by Maslow is based on recognition. This is where acceptance and the value of an employee by others are of utmost importance. The last level of Maslow's needs is self-actualization needs: Here, the employee is competent in the job and knows what exactly his or her role is as an individual in the organisation. The worker in this level achieves what they want in their work through experience (Erkilic, 2008).

To further clarify on Maslow's model, job satisfaction and work performance, Isaiah and Nenty (2012) state that, a teacher's basic needs: food, clothing and shelter should be met before he or she is expected to perform efficiently. Moreover, the safety needs, describe the teachers' feeling of physical and psychological safety and security which can affect the teachers' job satisfaction and work performance. As a result, a teacher who is insecure cannot perform his or her duties diligently.

Isaiah and Nenty's (2012) describe the belonging needs as the needs that focus on an employee's desire to be accepted and belonging to a particular group. As such, secondary school teachers, just like other professionals, also need to be part of a certain social group to fit well in the society. Therefore, teachers who feel isolated from others experience low job satisfaction and this negatively affects their work performance. The esteem needs focus on the recognition and pride which are parts of an effective teacher. For further clarity, the National Commission on Education (Botswana, 1993) pointed out that teachers have low status and their motivation was also rated low which indicated that they had low self-esteem. Isaiah and Nenty (2012) further established that when teachers develop in their work, they finally reach their potential and they termed that as self-actualization. However, they indicated that only a small number of the secondary school teacher population achieves this level.

Suleman and Hussain (2018) state that Maslow's model can be used to explain more on employees' job satisfaction because human beings only get happy when their needs are fulfilled. So, when the supervisors use Maslow's theory, Suleman and Hussain (2018) claim that the job satisfaction in workers is guaranteed as their individual needs will surely be fulfilled. They further indicate that, fulfilling such needs can be made possible by rewarding employees appropriately. For instance, the physiological needs of workers can be fulfilled by making sure that workers are provided with decent accommodation. Likewise, they mention that the workers' security needs can be fulfilled by giving them compensation, retirement pension and medical facilities. On the other hand, challenging responsibilities can fulfil the worker's esteem needs while training and difficulty task might be useful in achieving the teachers' self-actualization (Suleman & Hussain, 2018). Through this study, the researcher therefore wanted to find out the relevance of Maslow's hierarchy of needs in relation to how gender and the work environment influence the job satisfaction of public secondary school teachers in the Central region of Botswana.

Problem and purpose

Teachers' job performance is a societal concern which is most often inextricable from student performance. As such, learners' poor academic performance has always been attributed to teachers' lack of commitment; this predicament has been felt by teachers in the Central region of Botswana. The academic performance in the majority of public secondary schools in the region has been below expectations and teachers are continuously criticized for these outcomes. On the contrary, secondary school teachers associate students' poor academic performance to lack of job satisfaction and low work morale which are ascribed to the poor work environments. The drastic decline in student performance amongst the majority of secondary schools in Botswana was severely impacted by the 2011 civil servants industrial strike. It has been eight years since the massive two months strike happened, but the learners' academic performance has not yet improved.

This clearly shows that the poor working environment, unsatisfactory promotions and unattractive salaries which secondary school teachers have long lamented about have not yet been addressed. As a result, their job satisfaction level is adversely affected and this greatly contributes to the unsatisfactory teachers' work performance which ultimately affects the learners' academic performance (BOSETU newsletter, 2017). So, since gender has been often examined as a biographical factor in the job satisfaction studies as it has been revealed that there are some disparities between the work performance of male and female teachers, the researcher has been intrigued to investigate intensively on how gender and the work environment influence the job satisfaction of public secondary school teachers in the central region of Botswana. This is intended to come up with some recommendations which would address the unsatisfactory work performance amongst secondary teachers in Botswana and the Central region in particular.

Research questions

1. Does the job satisfaction of public secondary school teachers influence their work environment, promotion and their work performance?
2. Is there a relationship between the gender of public secondary school teachers and their job satisfaction, promotion and the work environment?

Research Hypotheses

Ho₁: The job satisfaction of secondary school teachers do not significantly influence their; work environment, promotion and the work performance.

Ho₂: Gender insignificantly influences the secondary school teachers' work environment and promotion.

Literature review

Job satisfaction and secondary teachers' work performance

Job satisfaction is very important not only to the employees but to the employers as well because it enhances productivity and decreases employee turnover. As a result, an effort to enhance the work performance

in schools will never be accomplished if teachers' job satisfaction is not taken into consideration. According to Syptak (1999), job satisfaction is an essential factor at work and has been linked to improved work performance as well as increased commitment amongst workers. This therefore means that, motivated and satisfied teachers tend to influence the students' learning positively while the opposite of that may have a negative impact on students' learning and academic results.

A study conducted by Parasuraman, Uli and Abdullah in 2009 indicates that very few work institutions have considered job satisfaction as a top priority. This is because they do not understand the significance of creating work environments that; interest, stimulate and maintain the hardworking employees in order to have productive and competitive organisations. In addition, Parasuraman et al (2009) found out that a great part of a person's life is spent in the workplace. As such, the life at work should be pleasing for an individual. Their study findings further revealed that the male respondents had a comparatively higher level of job satisfaction when compared to their female counterparts. However, the differences in job satisfaction between males and females in the Central region of Botswana are not clear.

It is imperative to note that job satisfaction is significant in the teaching occupation just like it is in other professions. Thus, a professionally satisfied secondary school teacher has a sociable mindset and greater passion for work. Such secondary school teachers contribute massively towards advancing the education of learners. However, unhappy secondary school teachers are generally realised to be ill-tempered, miserable, unfriendly and disturbed. Therefore, dissatisfied secondary school teachers usually affect the lives of learners negatively and cause massive harm to the learning institution and the community as a whole (Sankar & Vasudha, 2015).

A study conducted in Nigeria by Akomolafe and Ogunmakin in 2014 as cited in Mocheche, Bosire, Raburu (2017) stressed that the effects of job dissatisfaction on secondary school teachers among others include; absenteeism from school, turnover, aggressive behaviour towards core-workers and learners, early exit from teaching and emotional pulling out from work. It is therefore manifest that when teachers are not satisfied with their job, their performance at work is adversely affected.

Green (2000) emphasises that, to deal with the job satisfaction of workers has considerable effects on the employees themselves and also on their organisations. As a result, a satisfied teaching force leads to the highly committed and productive workforce because there would be lesser disturbance such as; absenteeism, the exit of 'good' employees, and incidences of harmful behaviour. Therefore, it is evident that there is a strong correlation between job satisfaction and teachers' work performance.

Gender, job satisfaction and teachers' work environment

Teachers' productivity in secondary schools is determined by numerous factors which influence their work performance. Among these factors, gender and the work environment are of great interest to the general populace mainly because there is a balance between males and females in the teaching profession particularly in the secondary level of education when compared to the past years when only females dominated the profession (Mabekoje, 2009). The findings on the nature of the relationship between gender, job satisfaction and the work environment have been far from being conclusive. However, in their study of secondary teachers in different schools, Crossman and Harris (2006) reported that male teachers were slightly more satisfied with their work environment than females.

It is significant to note that, job satisfaction amongst both males and females is very important in their working environment as it has been linked to factors like; effectiveness, non-attendance, turnover, and many others. As such, there have been several studies on the relationship between gender, the school environment and job satisfaction. Padilla (1993) therefore supports the notion that the work environment is linked to positive work related behaviour and improved performance. He argues that an unfavourable working environment in an organisation results in some of the workers leaving the institution as an indication that employees are not satisfied with their job. Moreover, a study conducted in Burkina Faso, Cameroon, Cote d'Ivoire, Madagascar and Senegal, Michaelewa (2002) discovered that large class sizes and inadequate school resources led to low job satisfaction and this negatively impacted on the teachers' work performance.

In 2013, Tilak conducted a survey which highlighted that male teacher enjoyed their challenging and interesting work; they were also happy with working long hours as they were rewarded fairly and had the opportunity for career development. In addition, another study conducted by Kaur and Sidana (2011) as cited in Mocheche, Bosire and Raburu (2017) also revealed that male teachers were more satisfied with their jobs than their female counterparts. When asked about how being a female affected their job satisfaction, a reasonable number of female teachers said that they did not achieve as they have wished and this affected their work performance.

It is important to note that a number of research studies have been carried out to compare the job satisfaction of male and female individuals in different contexts, including secondary schools (Hauret & Williams, 2017). In some research studies, no significant difference was found between the job satisfaction of males and females while in other many research studies it was found that males are more satisfied with their work environment as compared to females. On the other hand, some studies have established opposing findings in which they found that females are more satisfied with their job environment and the work itself than males. Rast and Tourani (2012) found that secondary teachers were moderately satisfied with their job and there was no significant difference between the job satisfaction of males and females with regard to their work environment.

Gender, job satisfaction and teachers' promotion

Wong and Wong (2010) indicate that teacher promotion is an imperative matter more especially because the salary levels in the education sector is different from those of the corporate world. The fact that the pay received by teachers is relatively low in most developing countries, promotion becomes the only approach used to increase such meagre salaries. In this way, teachers are expected to do their utmost in order to meet the standards stipulated by the employers so as to get a promotion. Through promotion, teachers are able to find roles which please them at different positions in the job hierarchy and this increases their productivity and work performance. Stagnant promotions amongst teachers negatively affect their commitment towards work, leading to low job performance and poor learners' academic results (Wong & Wong, 2010).

The gender/job satisfaction paradox (Kaiser, 2002 as quoted in Mabekoje, 2009) or the irony of the contented female worker refers to the fact that women report higher job satisfaction than men regardless of a clearly disadvantaged position in the labour market in terms of promotions and career prospects in most of the countries worldwide. A UNESCO report (2004) on education and gender suggested the establishment of gender equality in education policies and planned to make sure that there is equality as this showed that there are some inconsistencies associated with gender with regard to promotion in most schools. In the same vein, the 2004 ILO report as cited in Wong and Wong (2010) on labour standards advocated for equal opportunities in international labour markets to correct 'gender inequality' at work, including secondary schools. This emanated from the fact that the statistics from different schools showed that many males were being promoted than their female counterparts. This negatively affects the job satisfaction of the female teachers and they therefore tend to slow down at work thereby producing poor results.

Spector (1997) further observed that Scottish female teachers in secondary schools were promoted later than male teachers. He explained that most women had to contend with the difficulty of choosing to have a higher position and having to manage their homes. These he said were cited as barriers which limited female secondary school teachers from accepting some promotions. Furthermore, when conducting a study on promotion and gender, Ngimbudzi (2009) used a t-test to find out whether the job satisfaction level of male and female teachers had a significant difference on the basis of promotion. The findings revealed that more males were satisfied with promotion than females. He concluded that the variance in promotions affected the work performance of women teachers when compared to males.

Oluoch (2006) and Kagoda (2010) notes that the efforts made to equalise the access to promotions in education do not give reasonable results in some districts in Tanzania and Uganda respectively as well as other developing countries. In Uganda, most of the Headteachers and other senior posts in secondary schools are occupied by males. For this reason, there is need for gender equality to be considered during the deployment of

such posts. However, Oketch (2003) conducted a study on factors that contribute to job satisfaction and dissatisfaction among secondary school teachers in Homa bay district in Kenya. He discovered that, many male teachers were dissatisfied than female teachers with regard to promotion. He therefore recommended that in order to bridge the gap of promotion inconsistencies, gender equality should be taken into account.

Methodology

A quantitative approach was used for this study and it was considered to be the most appropriate method to examine how gender and the work environment influence the job satisfaction of public secondary school teachers in the Central region of Botswana. The decision to use this approach emanated from that the research used a questionnaire which permitted the researcher to use many teacher respondents during data collection so that generalizing the collected data would be achievable. This was also in conjunction with Leedy (1993) who emphasizes that a quantitative approach focuses on reliable and objective data as it employs very structured procedures which are made to validate determined hypotheses.

The study was also an inferential survey in which a questionnaire formed the basis of the research. The study targeted secondary school teachers in the Department of Public Service Management (DPSM) payroll who teach in public secondary schools in the Central region of Botswana. Both teachers from junior and senior secondary schools in the region were used. From the ten schools understudy, the population consisted of 680 teachers from the Central region records (Ministry of Education, n.d). The 420 teachers were from senior secondary schools. However, 260 were from junior secondary schools. Nevertheless, the target population consisted of 313 male teachers (167 were from senior secondary schools while 146 were from junior secondary schools). On the other hand, 367 teachers were females (198 were from junior secondary schools and 169 were from senior secondary schools).

Nyange recommends the use of larger samples in order to foster the accuracy of research results. The sample size was, therefore, 32% of the population which gave a sample of 213 teacher respondents from the 10 public secondary schools. The instrument's reliability was established using cronbach alpha estimates after trial testing and all the variables had an internal consistency index above .80.

Data analysis and interpretation of results

Ho: *The public secondary school teachers in the Central region of Botswana:*

- are not significantly satisfied with their job
- are significantly not satisfied with their work environment
- have a significant lack of promotion

This hypothesis was tested by carrying out five population t-test analysis of public secondary school teachers responses to (i) an item "job satisfaction" designed to measure the level to which teachers job satisfaction influences their work performance; (ii) The level to which the teachers' work environment influence their work performance; and (iii) The level to which the teachers' level of promotion influences their work performance.

For each of the three variables, the SPSS computer package was used to statistically analyze in order to compare the observed mean with the expected mean as it is shown in Table 1 below:

Table 1

One-Sample t-Test Analysis of the Level to which Teachers' Job Satisfaction, Work Environment, Promotion Influence their Work Performance

Variable	μ	\bar{X}	SD	Mean Diff	t-value	Sig

Job satisfaction	17.5	18.53	5.33	1.02	2.39	.018
Work performance	14	5.00	2.82	-9.00	-39.58	.000
Promotion	7	5.00	2.82	-2.00	-8.80	.000

$p < .05$ (2-tailed).

The teachers' perception of their job satisfaction in connection with their work performance, the t-value obtained was 2.39. This was found to be higher than the critical t-value of 1.96. Hence, the null hypothesis was retained. This then revealed that teachers in the Central region secondary school teachers are not happy with their job.

On the other hand, the teachers' view of their work environment in relation to their work performance as shown in Table 1 above, at- the value of -39.58 given was realised to be significant at .05 alpha level. This meant that the null hypothesis was still retained. As a result, this indicated that the public secondary school teachers in the Central region were not happy with their work environment.

Based on the collected data on teachers' promotion, the negative t-value of -8.80 was found to be significant at 0.5 alpha level. The results led to the null hypothesis being retained, which indicated that the public secondary school teachers in the Central region of Botswana had not been promoted and that makes them unhappy.

Ho₂: *Gender insignificantly influences the secondary school teachers' work environment and promotion.*

To test this hypothesis, an independent sample t-Test, was carried out to examine the magnitude of how gender influences teachers' perception of the work environment and promotion (see Table 2). Regarding the perception of public secondary school teachers' in the Central region on the work environment, the data analysis gave an F-value of 13.37 with 152 and 146 degrees of freedom. This indicated a significant influence beyond the .05 alpha level. As such, the null hypothesis was retained.

As for the teachers' promotion, the public secondary school teachers in the Central region of Botswana gave an F-value of 13.37 with 152 and 146 degrees of freedom. Therefore, this led the null hypothesis being retained. However, it is important to note that there is a significant difference in mean scores for males ($M=4.36$, $SD=2.43$) and females ($M=5.63$, $SD=3.05$) as shown in Table 3. It is worth noting to acknowledge that, many females show some dissatisfaction on the work environment than male respondents. In short, gender has a significant influence on the perceptions of teachers regarding their work environment and promotion.

Table 2

Independent Sample t-Test Regarding The Influence Of Gender On The Work Environment And The Promotion Of Secondary School Teachers In The Central Region Of Botswana.

		Independent Samples test				
		Levene's Test for Equality of variables		t-test for equality of Means		
		F	Sig	t	df	Sig (2 tailed)
Variables	Equal variance assumed					
Work environment	Equal variance assumed	13.37	.000	-2.87	152 146.26	.005
Promotion	Equal variance assumed	13.37	.000	-2.87	152 146.26	.005

Table 3

Descriptive Statistics on the Influence of Gender On the Work Environment and The Promotion of Secondary Schools teachers in the Central Region of Botswana.

Group statistics

Variables	Gender of respondents	N	Mean	Std Deviation
Work environment	Male	76	4.36	2.43
	Female	78	5.63	3.05
Promotion	Male	76	4.36	2.43
	Female	78	5.63	3.05

Summary of the findings

Job satisfaction is an essential factor at work and has been linked to improved work performance as well as increased commitment amongst workers. As a result, motivated and satisfied teachers influence students' learning positively while demotivated teachers affect learners' academic performance negatively. It is crucial to note that job satisfaction is significant in the teaching occupation just like it is in indifferent professions. Thus, a professionally satisfied secondary school teacher has a sociable mindset and works hard for the betterment of the school results. Moreover, job satisfaction amongst both males and females is vital in their working environment. This has been linked to teachers' effectiveness, non-attendance, turnover, and complacency in the workplace. As such, there have been several studies on the relationship between gender, the school environment and job satisfaction. While some research studies discovered no significant differences between the job satisfaction of males and females, other studies found that males are more satisfied with their work environment and their job when compared to females. On the other hand, some studies have established opposing findings in which they found that females are more satisfied with their job environment and the work itself than males. However, with promotions, research has revealed that more males are satisfied with promotion than females.

Discussions, Conclusions and recommendations**Discussions**

Gender has a significant influence on the perception of teachers regarding their work environment and promotion. The findings of this study revealed that female teachers were dissatisfied with their job when compared to males. Tilak (2013) concurs with these study findings as he had established that the job satisfaction level of male teachers was high when compared to that of the female teachers. The male secondary school teachers according to Tilak (2013) enjoyed their work, which they deemed as interesting and demanding. They were also happy with the working hours, good remuneration and the opportunity for professional growth and promotion. In addition, research by Mondal (2014) agreed with this study findings. The research found out that the mean of job satisfaction scores for male and female teachers was found to be 219.54 (SD =24.42) and 218.80 (SD = 21.17) respectively. This therefore meant that males' job satisfaction was slightly higher than that of female teachers.

However, this study is contrary to the results obtained by Parasuraman, Uli and Abdullar (2009) who concluded that female teachers are highly satisfied with their job environment than their male counterparts. Moreover, Njiru (2014) further the results found by Parasuraman et al (2009), on job satisfaction and motivation among secondary school teachers in Kenya. He indicated that females were happier with their job as they related well with others and in a co-operative way, despite that the job was more challenging. "Out of 30 secondary school teachers who participated in the study, 17 (56.7%) were female while 13(43.3%) were male" (Njiru, 2014, p. 140). As a result, female teachers had significantly higher levels of job satisfaction than their male counterparts.

On the other hand, Gruneberg (1979, p. 175), mentions that "Early research on gender and job satisfaction indicated that the findings of investigations on gender differences and job satisfaction are somewhat inconsistent and contradictory, and show no clear significant correlation. Various researchers have come to different conclusions regarding the correlation between gender and job satisfaction. Some studies show women employees to be more satisfied than men, while other studies show men as being more satisfied than women.

Conclusions

Job satisfaction is essential not only to the employees but also to the employers because it enhances productivity and improves work performance. If secondary school teachers are dissatisfied, this usually affects the academic of learners negatively and causes massive harm to the learning institution and the entire community. As such, a satisfying teaching force leads to highly committed and productive workforce because there would be lesser disturbance such as; absenteeism, the exit of 'good' employees, and incidences of harmful behaviour. Unhappy secondary school teachers are generally realised to be ill-tempered, miserable, unfriendly and disturbed. Therefore, dissatisfied secondary school teachers usually affect the lives of learners in a profound way. A significant difference in levels of job satisfaction with regard to the work environment and promotion was found between male teachers and female teachers, with male participants reporting greater job satisfaction.

Recommendations

- The Ministry of Basic Education should provide conducive teaching and learning environments in secondary schools in the Central region of Botswana.
- The school management should ensure that both male and female teachers are recommended for promotions for gender equality.
- The Ministry of Basic Education should implement policies and strategies that seek to promote gender equality and job satisfaction amongst teachers in schools in order to promote productively and student-academic performance.
- Future researchers should conduct an intensive research in which mixed methods will be employed to establish the relationship between gender, the work environment and job satisfaction on secondary school teachers' effectiveness.

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